

REVIEW ARTICLE

Stevia rebaudiana – A review on agricultural, chemical and industrial applications

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Abstract

Stevia rebaudiana a perennial shrub of genus *Stevia* and family Asteraceae is a plant, native to Paraguay while it has been grown in many countries around the world for commercial purpose. The leaf extract of stevia has a sweet taste profile resulted by a group of chemical compounds called Glycosides. Stevia extract is used as a natural sweetener which replaces the sugar or can be marketed as a non-caloric sweetener. The diterpene glycosides in the Stevia leaf extract are responsible for the sweet taste whereas the main responsible glycosides for the sweetening property are Stevioside and Rebaudiosides A. The bitter aftertaste and the natural licorice taste in Stevia is due to high Stevioside/ Rebaudiosides A ratio. Therefore, a promising sugar substitute for the market can be made with a low ratio of Stevioside/ Rebaudiosides A which can be achieved through different techniques such as enzymatic glycosylation and breeding between desirable genotypes. Stevia is used in food industry, medicine industry and by product industry (fertilizer, animal feed). In addition to its sweetening property, Stevia has numerous therapeutic effects including anti-diabetic, anti-hypertension, anti-cancer, antioxidant, anti-obesity and anti-microbial effects. However, there are several controversial ideas on the safety of Stevia consumption in humans while many studies in-vitro and in-vivo have revealed no health risk in consumption of Steviol glycosides.

Keywords: Stevia, Stevioside, Glycoside, Rebaudiosides A, Natural Sweetner

Introduction

Stevia plant is scientifically known as *Stevia rebaudiana* Bertoni which is also called as sweet leaf, sugar leaf, sweet herb, sugar weed. It is a member of the family Asteraceae. It is a small perennial shrub which grows up to 65 cm tall. It has a leaf structure of oppositely arranged lanceolate to oblanceolate leaves, serrated above the middle. Trichome structures on Stevia leaf surface have two distinct sizes, one large (4–5 µm), one small (2.5 µm) (Shaffert and Chetobar, 1994). It has been used for centuries as a bio-sweetener and a medicine. Its white crystalline compound (glycoside) is the natural herbal sweetener. This compound which carries no calories is over 100-300 times sweeter than table sugar (Goyal et al., 2010).

Genus *Stevia* is reported to have 154 members in which only *Stevia rebaudiana* and another species produce sweet steviol glycosides. Stevia is a plant native to the valley of the Rio Monday in highlands of North-eastern Paraguay in South America. It grows in sandy soils on the marshland edges, acid infertile sand or muck soils. Apart from its native land, Stevia is grown in Brazil, Canada, USA, China, Korea, Taiwan, Japan, and United Kingdom for the

commercialization purpose. Out of them, China reports the largest cultivation area. The usage of Stevia leaves has years of history where it had been traditionally used for hundreds of years in Paraguay and Brazil to sweeten local teas and medicines. The leaves of Stevia accumulate the highest steviol glycoside content composing 4%–20% of the dry weight but the actual abundance of steviol glycoside differs between cultivars (Lemus-Mondaca et al., 2012). In addition to the sweetening property, Stevia is known to have different therapeutic activities. The stevia leaves have the potential to be used as a functional food and nutritional supplement (Zhang et al., 2017). The leaf extract is claimed to have anti-cancer, anti-diabetic, anti-hypertension, anti-microbial, antioxidant, anti-obesity and anti-cancer properties.

Figure 1: Leaves and flowers of stevia (*Stevia rebaudiana*) (Photo credits and rights: Gilles Paire)

Crop Cultivation and Processing

Plant propagation is done using seeds and cuttings. However, seed germination rates are very low resulting difficulties in finding seedlings for large scale production. As reported by Shock (1982), in the wild it reproduces by seed, crown division, or rooting of branches that lodge or are trampled by cattle. Production of viable seed is erratic. In wild it is a small perennial shrub but in cultivation it grows three feet or more in height while the branching and tillering are also prominent. The tolerance to water stress is poor. Therefore, frequent shallow irrigation is needed. It grows well in sandy soil and has the ability withstand acid infertile soil. Salt tolerance is said to be poor therefore, should not be grown in saline soils or with soils with low water quality. Competition with weeds is poor, so controlling of weeds during Stevia cultivation is necessary (Shock, 1982).

The leaf yield and accumulation patterns of stevioside may vary depending on the environmental conditions. Therefore, investigating the nutritional variations under different agro-climatic conditions would provide leads for developing strategies to increase the productivity (Pal et al., 2015). Long days favor leaf yields and leaf stevioside concentration (Metvier and Viana, 1979). Consequently, plant growth in temperate areas with long summer days would be ideal for high stevioside yields. However, the reduced seed production would be a drawback (Shock, 1982). Since glycoside synthesis is reduced at or just before flowering, delaying flowering with long days allows more time for glycoside accumulation.

Stevia is harvested just prior to flowering when steviol glycoside content in the leaves is at its maximum (Sumida, 1980; Xiang, 1983). The whole plant is harvested just above ground level, elevated into wagons and then dried. Drying of the stem and soft green leaf material is completed immediately after harvesting using a drying wagon, a kiln or done naturally in case of large-scale production. The effect of drying conditions on glycoside levels and processing quality of the leaves needs more research.

Drying can be conducted in a shade, home dehydrator or using simple drying racks inside transparent poly house or transparent glass roofing or by-passing dry air just above room temperature (Hossain et al., 2017; Gantait et al., 2018). However, sun drying is known to be a preferred method with no excessive heat and good air circulation. On a moderate warm day, stevia can be quickly dried under sun in about 12 hours. Longer drying time can result low stevioside content (Hossain et al., 2017). Drying stevia under artificial conditions is affected by number of factors including loading rate, temperature, and ambient air conditions (Van Hooren and Lester, 1990). Depending on weather conditions and density of loading, it generally takes 24 to 48 hours to dry stevia at 40 to 500⁰ C (Hossain et al., 2017).

After adequate drying, the leaves are stripped of the stems / twigs using a thresher/ hand, packed and stored in a cool and dry place (Hossain et al., 2017).

Artificial drying and threshing can be employed for leaf separation in large-scale commercial production process. Generally, the stems which have low concentrations of sweet glycosides are removed in order to minimize the processing costs (Brandle and Rosa, 1992). The separated leaves are processed in special factories to extract rebaudioside A with high sweetening properties. Except for the leaves, the remaining parts of the plant, including stems, seeds, flowers and even leaves that were not selected for industrialization, are collected and processed into animal feed or fertilizers.

Pest Attacks in *Stevia rebaudiana*

Stevia plant being a non-toxic, has been found to have insect-repelling tendencies. The aphids and other bugs that find the sweet taste not to their taste is a natural defense mechanism against pests. Therefore, even the crop-devouring grasshoppers have been reported to bypass stevia under cultivation. This feature makes stevia a good crop to promote resilience from pest infestation and a short-term crop to strengthen climate change adaptation to mitigate its adverse impacts in agriculture (Karanja, 2021).

Two fungal diseases, *Septoria steviae* and *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum*, have been reported in stevia grown in Canada (Lovering and Reeleder 1996; Chang et al., 1997). *Septoria* disease is characterized by depressed, angular, shiny olive gray lesions, sometimes surrounded by a chlorotic halo, that rapidly coalesce. *Sclerotinia* disease is characterized by brown lesions on the stem, near the soil line, followed by wilting and eventually by the complete collapse of affected (Brandle et al., 1998). Due to the slow establishing nature of stevia and low completability with weeds, herbicides or other means are required to control weed growth to produce ample yield and a clean crop. The herbicide trifluralin appears to be well tolerated by stevia (Katayama et al., 1976).

Chemistry of *Stevia Sweetener*

Fresh leaves have a mild licorice flavor. This is the simplest form of steviol glycoside in its most natural and unrefined state. The leaves of stevia have a pleasantly sweet and refreshing taste that can linger in the mouth for hours. The material contains the sweet components surrounded by the bitter components in the veins (Maiti and Purohit, 2008).

Stevia sweeteners are extracted from the dried leaves, clarified and crystallized. The sweet constituents of stevia include eight diterpene glycosides: stevioside, steviolbioside, rebaudiosides A, B, C, D, E, and dulcoside A, which collectively are 100–300 times sweeter than sucrose. Of these eight glycosides, two main glycosides are Stevioside and

Rebaudioside A. Stevioside is 300 times sweeter than sugar (Ranjan et al., 2011). Stevioside content is 5-10% of the dry weight of the leaves and Rebaudioside A is 2-4%. Dulcoside A and Rebaudiosides C (1-2%) are the other main components. Minor glycosides include flavonoid glycosides, coumarins, cinnamic acids, phenylpropanoids and some essential oils (Kinghorn, 1987). However, as per Singh and Verma (2015), leaves of stevia contain around 10 sweetening glycosides of which stevioside (3-10%), rebaudioside-A (13%), and rebaudioside-B, C, D are important. Triterpenes, amyirin acetate, three esters of lupeol and the sterols like stigmasterol, sitosterol and campesterol can also be extracted from the leaves (Nabeta et al., 1976).

Although steviol glycosides are generally sweet, organoleptic properties of individual steviol glycoside depend on the combination of sugar moieties attached to steviol glycoside (Hellfritsch et al., 2012). Therefore, other than increasing overall steviol glycoside content, there is also a preference for Stevia varieties that can produce more pleasant tasting steviol glycoside in greater proportions.

As per studies conducted by Gloria (2013), stevioside is 300 times sweeter than sucrose. It shows a sweetness profile similar to that of sucrose, except that it has an unpleasant, persistent, menthol, and bitter aftertaste. Stevioside is a white powder, highly soluble in water, ethanol and methanol, and is nonfermentable. The heat and pH tolerance and stability of stevioside has been observed to be very high, retaining the sweetness with little or no loss.

Rebaudioside A is the second most abundant sweet diterpene glycoside in the leaves of stevia and is more superior to stevioside with respect to sweetness and lack of a bitter aftertaste (Ahmad et al., 2020). Rebaudioside A is even more stable, sweeter, and has a better taste profile than stevioside (Gloria, 2003).

Medicinal Use of Stevia rebaudiana

Phytochemical property in Stevia rebaudiana

Apart from its sweeteners, Stevia also contains essential amino acids, fatty acids, and other health beneficial bioactive compounds including non-glycosidic labdane diterpenes, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, crude fiber, phytosterols, chlorogenic acids, triterpenes and hydrocarbons (Wolwer-Rieck, 2012). The glycosides found in Stevia have phytochemical properties (Kinghorn, 1984). Stevia contains a high percentage of phenols, flavonoids and antioxidant activity (Taleie et al., 2012). Furthermore, Stevia leaves' extracts are found to contain phytochemicals, such as phenols which are the key compounds accountable for the antioxidant activity of the extracts (Kim et al., 2011). Similarly, phytochemical analysis of the leaves by some researchers revealed the presence of steroids and alkaloids in large quantities together with tannins, flavonoids, saponins, glycoside, sterol, anthraquinones, triterpenes, reducing compounds, vitamin C, folic acid, all of the essential amino acids, non-glycosidic diterpenes, chlorogenic acids, nutrients, vitamins, and other minor compounds (Tadhani and Subhash, 2006; Lemus-Mondaca et al., 2012; Wolwer-Rieck, 2012). In addition to steviol glycosides, the leaves of the stevia plant may also contain other phytoconstituents, such as polyphenols, flavonoids, carotenoids, tannins, phenolic acids, chlorogenic acids, fatty acids, amino acids, proteins, and vitamins (Abou-Arab et al., 2010; Muanda et al., 2011; Gawel-Beben et al., 2015; Karakose et al., 2015).

Effect on Hypertension and Cardiovascular system

Favorable effect of stevia on blood pressure has been reported. The plant may have cardiogenic actions, which normalizes blood pressure and regulates heartbeat. The plant has displayed vasodilatory actions in both normotensive and hypertensive animals. Stevia has decreased blood pressure and has increased diuretic and natriuretic effects in rats (Ranjan et al., 2011). In a study conducted by Chan et al. (2000), 106 hypertensive women aged between 28 and 75 years were administered 0.25 g stevioside three-times daily found a reduction in both the systolic and diastolic blood pressures by 14 mmHg and 14.3 mmHg respectively, after just seven days. This hypotensive effect persisted throughout the entire duration of the study (1 year) with no side effects or significant changes in blood parameters (such as glucose and lipid levels) being reported. As a result, Chan et al. (2000), suggested the use of oral stevioside as an alternative or supplementary treatment for hypertension.

Effect on Diabetes Mellitus

The leaves of stevia are the source of steviol glycosides (mainly stevioside and rebaudioside) which are estimated to be 300 times sweeter than sugar but also have no effect on blood sugar, so it is helpful for hypo glycemia and type-2 diabetes ((Midmore and Rank, 2002; Soejarto, 2002; Ramesh et al., 2006). Animal studies suggest that Stevia may be helpful in treating diabetes. Steviol, isosteviol and glucosteviol decreased glucose production in rat renal cortical. Stevioside lowered blood glucose in type-II diabetic in fatty rats when given orally (Ranjan et al., 2011). It was found that those who were treated with a stevia preload showed a significant decrease in both the postprandial glucose and postprandial insulin levels when compared to the subjects that were treated with either an aspartame or sucrose preload (Anton et al., 2010)

Steviol regulates blood glucose level by enhancement of insulin secretion as well as insulin utilization in insulin deficient animals and is also used as a digestive tonic. It is expected to bring hope to diabetic people who have craving for sweets (Ranjan et al., 2011).

Anti-microbial effect

Different studies have claimed that Stevia leaf extract possesses anti-fungal and anti-bacterial properties in addition to its other versatile uses. The stevia leaf extract in different solvent medium have produced different results of anti-microbial activity. As per the study conducted by Debnath (2008), crude leaf extract in water was found to be ineffective against microbial activity. However, satisfactory results have been reported from the crude leaf extract in chloroform and methanol against bacterial activity for the strains of *Escherichia coli*, *Streptococcus mutans*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Anti-fungal activity reported differently in both of the extract where crude leaf extract in methanol has successfully suppressed the growth of *Sclerotinia minor* and *Curvularia Stevia* while chloroform crude leaf extract possessed antifungal property only on *Sclerotinia minor* whereas this study was tested on six fungal species (*Aspergillus niger*, *Curvularia lunata*, *Sclerotinia minor*, *Rhizopus*, *Alternaria alternate* and *Microsporum gypseum*) (Debnath, 2008).

Stevioside suppresses the growth of oral microorganisms. It can safely be used in herbal medicines, in daily usage products such as mouthwashes and toothpastes. Mild stevia leaf tea also offers excellent relief for an upset stomach (Goyal et al., 2010). It also showed antibacterial, antiseptic, anti-inflammatory which has shown good results in clearing up skin problems like acne, dermatitis, eczema (Ranjan et al., 2011).

Anti-cancer Activity

Various studies suggest promising health benefits of Stevia for cancer, dental cavities, oxidative stress and microbial infections (Ahmad et al., 2020). As per the review conducted by Talevi (2018), the first study to show the anti-tumour effect of stevia dates back to 1997 carried out by Toyoda et al. (1997), where stevioside-treated female rats showed a significantly lower incidence of adenomas of the mammary gland when compared to controls (Toyoda et al., 1997; Talevi, 2018). As a solution to the developing resistance of cells to the chemotherapeutic agents, new agents include phytochemicals such as Stevia will be a promising hope for cancer patients (Li et al., 2017). Diabetic rodents treated with stevia leaf extract and powder respectively, resulted in a decrease in the lipid peroxidation as well as favorable changes in other anti-oxidation markers (Shivanna et al., 2013; Singh et al., 2013).

Steviol in Stevia is found to have anti-cancer activity in gastro-intestinal cells (Chen et al., 2018) and in human breast cancer cells (Gupta et al., 2017). According to Paul et al. (2012), stevioside was also found to possess anti-proliferative action against the MCF-7 breast cancer cell line through the induction of apoptosis and DNA synthesis inhibition.

Industrial Use of Stevia

In September 1995, the USA FDA allowed Stevia and its extracts to be imported as a food supplement but not as a sweetener. Major food companies like Coca-Cola and Beatrice Foods used Stevia extracts to sweeten the foods for sale in Japan, Brazil and other countries. Statistics indicate that in some countries up to 30 % of their needed sugar is replaced by stevioside-like sweetness products.

Stevioside is available in three purity ranges: crude extract, 50% and 90% purity. Since 1970, stevia sweeteners have been used in a wide range of food and beverage applications in Japan, including soft drinks, candies, chocolate, chewing gum, ice cream, yogurt, jam, pudding, and table-top sweeteners. It is commonly used in combination with sucrose and fructose and also with other sweeteners such as aspartame, cyclamate, and acesulfame-K, but not with saccharin. It is currently approved for use in Japan, Taiwan, and Mercosur. An acceptable daily intake of stevioside for humans of 7.94 mg per kilogram of body weight has been suggested.

The most abundant steviol glycoside usually found in stevia leaf extract is stevioside, which has a bitter aftertaste, therefore limiting its commercial application in foods as a high-potency sweetener (De Roode et al., 2015). Passionfruit juice sweetened with stevia showed bitter aftertaste, bitter taste, and metallic flavor, as well as had lower acceptance regarding texture, aroma, flavor, and overall impression (Rocha and Bolini, 2015). The elimination of the bitter aftertaste in steviol glycosides is a key challenge for manufacturers (De Roode et al., 2015).

One of the commonly used strategies to improve the taste of stevioside is through the process of glycosylation. The rebaudioside compound has the same aglycon structure as stevioside but with one glucose less and it has been found through a comprehensive study, that the rebaudioside can be obtained from stevioside by enzymatic transformation (Izawa et al., 2010).

Using the enzyme α -amylase extracted from *Aspergillus oryzae* or *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* in the presence of soluble starch, stevioside can be trans-glycosylated. This process known as enzymatic trans-glycosylation has increased the sweetness of the stevioside while masking the reducing the bitter aftertaste (Ye et al., 2013; 2014). Enzymatic trans-glycosylation of stevioside has also been performed using the enzyme cyclodextrin glucosyltransferase (Yu et

al., 2015), dextransucrase (Ko et al., 2016), alternansucrase (Musa et al., 2014) and several other enzymes (Gerwig et al., 2016) which has resulted the latter benefits.

Another strategy to minimize the bitter aftertaste of steviol glycosides is microencapsulation in which spray-drying techniques, with inulin and maltodextrin as encapsulation agents, are used (Chranioti et al., 2016).

Another method to obtain steviol glycosides with good organoleptic properties is through selective breeding of different Stevia plants with different desirable genotypes. The demand for higher rebaudioside A content and low stevioside content in stevia is promising for the market since it has a less bitter after taste. The native rebaudioside A / stevioside ratio in Stevia leaves is usually about 0.5 or less (Yadav et al., 2011). Stevia plants with decreased content of stevioside and a higher content of rebaudioside A gives leaf extracts with less bitter aftertaste. Through selective breeding of stevia, new varieties of stevia, including a novel cultivar *Stevia rebaudiana morita*, has been developed. It can produce higher ratio of rebaudioside A to stevioside (Kaplan and Turgut, 2019; Kim et al., 2019).

Wheat bread has been made with stevia extract to maintain the antioxidant property (Ruiz et al., 2015). As per a study conducted by Capella and colleagues in 2019, fruit juice sweetened with stevia has shown a greater concentration of phenolic compounds and antioxidant property compared to the fruit juice not sweetened with stevia (Carbonell-Capella et al., 2019)

Leaders in carbonated beverage industry (Coca-Cola Co, Pepsi, Atlanta have already introduced stevia as a sweetening source of their soft drinks. (Gelski, 2016). For example, Coca-Cola Lite sweetened with stevia and cane sugar (90 calories per 12oz. serving); Pepsi True, a low-calorie stevia-sweetened beverage (100calories per 355-ml can, versus 150 calories in regular Pepsi); and Stubborn Soda containing stevia and cane sugar (90–100 calories per 12-oz. bottle), have been introduced recently (Hartman, 2017). Furthermore, ready-to-drink iced tea products containing stevia as an ingredient have increased 86% over the last five years all over the world. Since 2010, over 300 teas have been introduced which contain stevia. When formulating a low-calorie tea, stevia is currently being used almost as often as sucralose (PureCircle, 2017).

Kulfi, a frozen dairy product with a 50% of sucrose is replaced by Stevia has received more sensory acceptance than the original. However, replacing more than 50% of sucrose by stevia has resulted negative acceptance from customers (Giri et al., 2014).

Temperature, pH and acids can affect the sweetness and quantity of the stevioside and rebaudioside. Stevioside has reported good stability at high temperature where a loss of 0-6% of sweetness has resulted during the heating at 60 °C for 6 days. Therefore this stability of stevioside against high temperatures makes it a suitable sweetener for cooked and baked foods and for beverages. However, considerable decomposition occurs at pH 10. Some degradation of stevioside and rebaudioside has been observed in carbonated beverages acidified with phosphoric and citric acids during storage at 37 °C.

While Stevia is mainly used as a sweetener and flavor enhancer in the food and beverage industry, its second and third market had been health market and by-product market. The by products are made as fertilizers and animal food. As per the studies conducted by Hossain et al. (2017), The remaining parts of the plant, including stems, seeds, flowers and even leaves that were not selected for industrialization, are collected and processed into animal feed or fertilizers.

Safety of *Stevia rebaudiana*

Safety of stevia sweeteners has been the subject of controversy for many years (Pendergast, 1991; Bonvie et al., 1997). However, high-purity stevia leaf extracts have been approved or adopted for use in foods and beverages in more than 150 countries and regions, including the European Union, the United States, the Middle East, New Zealand, Australia, China, Canada, Japan, Korea, India, Malaysia, Mexico, Brazil, Paraguay, Egypt, Chile, Argentina, Ghana, Kenya, South Africa, and many other countries in Asia, Africa, Europe, and Latin America (Samuel et al., 2018).

Planas and Kuc (1968) reported that a 5% solution of stevia leaf extract had a strong anti-fertility effect in both male and female rats. However, subsequent studies conducted to confirm this result have all been negative (Sincholle and Marcorelles, 1989; Yodyingyuad and Bunyawong, 1991). In addition, various studies have reported that steviol glycosides of stevia leaves are not teratogenic, carcinogenic and mutagenic, and cause no sub-acute or acute toxicity (Das et al., 1992; Abbas Momtazi-Borojeni et al., 2017). An LD₅₀ of 8.2 g kg⁻¹ for refined stevioside extract has been determined by Katayama et al. (1976). Xili et al. (1992) suggested an acceptable daily stevioside intake of 7.9 mg kg⁻¹. Yodyingyuad and Bunyawong (1991) reported that neither growth nor reproduction was affected in hamsters fed pure stevioside at levels up to 2.5 g kg⁻¹ d⁻¹ for 4 months. Pezzuto and co-workers (1985) reported that metabolically activated steviol is mutagenic, a result that has been confirmed in another study (Matsui et al., 1996). Kinghorn and Soejarto (1985) and Kinghorn (1992) conducted two reviews of the literature related to safety of stevia sweeteners and concluded that leaves and stevioside are safe for human consumption.

However, the activated steviol metabolite that is mutagenic has not yet been identified and it is not known if the activation of steviol actually occurs in humans (Procinska et al., 1991; Matsui et al., 1996). A study conducted in 2005 concluded that stevioside is not involved in bladder carcinogenesis (Mizushina et al., 2005). It is suitable for patients with diabetics, and Phenylketonuria, as well as for obese people who want to lose weight by avoiding sucrose in their diet. Moreover, no allergic reactions or toxicities have been found after its consumption (Geuns, 2002).

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